

CONTENT AND TYPES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF THE TEACHER.

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Abstract: In this article, the issue of content and types of pedagogical innovation activity of the teacher is scientifically and theoretically analyzed.

Key words: Innovation, content, analysis, assessment, task, pedagogical experience, level of innovation, stage, introduction of experience, obtaining information, etc.

In order to make reasonable proposals for improving the training of pedagogical personnel for general secondary schools, it is necessary to have a clear idea about the content of the innovative activities of these personnel.

In the general system of working on the model, since the scope of our research is limited to the study of the content of the teacher's innovative activity, it is our main task to highlight and scientifically justify the most important and typical manifestations of professional-pedagogical activity for this specialist.

Analysis of literature (V.A. Slastenin, L.S. Podo'mova, E.P. Morozov, P.I. Pidkasisto'i, V.S. Lazerev, N.V. Konoplina, N.R. Yusufbeko, etc.) and observations made it possible to compile a list of innovative activities for today. More than 50 types of activities implemented. In order to deliver the received materials in a more systematic way, we divided them into classes of different levels according to certain symptoms when developing a standard list

The stages of activity analysis are determined by the dimension of its interpretation. The dimension of interpretation means the number of the basis of classification, and it corresponds to the number of dimensions of the object. These dimensions consist of several gradations, respectively. Different types of innovative activities A symptom can be distinguished: methods of implementation, description of time and space, emotional tension and management. However, the most important thing in distinguishing one type of activity from another is the difference in their subjects (objects).

The object, in general, the activities of students of general secondary schools are realized in forms. Each of these forms has its own private object.

The objects of the teacher's innovative activity are students and pedagogical innovation (as the main object, the teacher's innovative activity differs from the activity of a teacher who teaches in a traditional way).

However, "any activity includes the goal, means, result, and activity process itself." Therefore, at the first level, we divided activities into classes based on two bases: the object of activity and the goal. As a result, four groups were formed, which we we called types of activities.

The goal of the first type - "Activity of transfer of innovative experience" is to introduce pedagogical innovations into the content of the educational process. The object can be any innovation that has been developed (existing) in addition to students. The second type of activity - "development of pedagogical innovations" has a different, sufficiently complex object (educational, didactic, management, etc.) and a different goal (discovery, invention, proposal, improvement of the stages of the educational process).

The basis for classifying the activity at the second level is the task. According to S.T. Turgunov, the task is a goal given under specific conditions {23} the conditions that turn the general goal into a specific task are considered to be the time and place of the activity. Thus, at the second level, there are four bases (object, purpose, place and time) was classified.

We will look at the first type of activity - "Transfer of innovative experience". It includes three classes of activities that differ in terms of the tasks that teachers of general secondary schools should solve.

The first stage is "analysis and evaluation of news content"; its task is to analyze and evaluate the level of novelty of pedagogical experience. The second stage is "analysis of the introduction of experience and its evaluation"; task - to get information on the scope of its implementation. The third stage - "developing a mechanism for transferring innovative proposals"; The task is to draw up a development plan for the acquisition of new activities. As the second type of activity, "development of pedagogical innovations" includes four stages of activity. The first stage is "critical analysis of practice", the task of which is to determine the degree of processing of the problem in the theory and practice of pedagogy. The second stage is "solving the problem search for ideas", its task is to establish existing conflicts, to choose methods and methods of solving them. "Development of innovative projects" is the third stage, and its task is to evaluate the results.

The third type of activity is "conducting pedagogical experiments-tests" and includes four stages of activity. The first stage is "setting goals"; task - performing the main tasks of the test; the second stage - "planning" - involves developing a research program, raising the main question. The task of the third

stage - "transfer" is to obtain new scientific information that proves the assumption based on the conducted research using the necessary methods.

The fourth type of activity called "transfer of innovative experience" also includes four stages of activity, each stage has specific tasks. If the first stage, i.e. "setting goals" implies the separation of the main tasks of transmitting new pedagogical ideas, the second stage - "task planning" is to determine the composition and sequence of actions for the transmission of news, to develop calendar plans-graphs. The third stage, known as the "transmission process", requires the implementation of an effective didactic process, that is, the organization of goal-oriented learning activities of students. monitors and evaluates.

The conclusion is that the analysis of the content of the work of the teacher-innovator, as expected, showed that a lot of time is spent on the transfer and transfer of innovative experience, that is, the educational process and its preparation. (Types I and IV -68.3 percent). However, almost a third of the teacher's working time is devoted to the development of pedagogical innovations (type II - 30.9 percent). A lot of time is spent on technical and methodical support and analysis of its results during the pedagogical test (6.2 percent). This fact, of course, can significantly reduce the time spent by preparing the experimental work in advance and reworking the stages of conducting the research.

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